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MODERN ELECTRONICS AND ENERGETICS”
dedicated to the 75th anniversary of the birth of Professor G.Gulomov,
Doctor of Physics and Mathematics**

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INTERBAND THREE-PHOTON ABSORPTION IN CRYSTALS IN THE THREE-BAND KANE MODEL (PART 2)

Rasulov Rustam Yavkachovich, professor of Fergana State University,
E-mail: r_rasulov51@mail.ru

Muminov Islomjon Arabboyevich, associate professor of physics department of Fergana State University,

Nasirov Mardon Xaldarbekovich, doctoral student of the department of physics of Fergana State University

Mamatova Maxliyo Adhamovna, senior teacher of the department of physics of Fergana State University

Abstract. The spectral dependences of the coefficients of interband three-photon optical transitions for InSb and for some optical transitions are calculated and a numerical analysis of

the coefficient of interband three-photon absorption of light is carried out, which taken into account the contribution to the three-photon absorption of optical transitions occurring during the simultaneous absorption of two photons in the Kane model.

Keywords: light absorption coefficient, photon, crystal, electron, holes.

Аннотация. Рассчитаны спектральные зависимости коэффициентов межзонных трёхфотонных оптических переходов для InSb и некоторых оптических переходов, а также проведён численный анализ коэффициента межзонного трёхфотонного поглощения света, учитывающий вклад оптических переходов, происходящих при одновременном поглощении двух фотонов в модели Кейна.

Ключевые слова: коэффициент поглощения света, фотон, кристалл, электрон, дырки.

Annotatsiya. InSb uchun va ba’zi optik o’tishlar uchun zonalararo uch fotonli optik o’tish koeffitsientlarining spektral bog‘liqliklari hisoblab chiqilgan va zonalararo uch fotonli yorug‘lik yutilishi koeffitsienti bo‘yicha sonli tahlil o‘tkazilgan, bunda Keyn modelida ikki fotonning bir vaqtning o‘zida yutilishi davomida sodir bo‘ladigan optik o’tishlarning uch fotonli yutilishga qo‘shgan hissasi hisobga olingan.

Kalit so‘zlar: yorug‘lik yutilish koeffitsienti, foton, kristall, elektron, kovaklar.

In the first part of this work, interband three-photon optical transitions in crystals of the In Sb type are classified and the spectral dependence of some optical transitions is analyzed. Next, we investigate the spectral dependence of the coefficient of three-photon interband absorption of polarized light in narrow-gap crystals in the three-band Kane approximation. As in the first part of this work, the three-photon interband light absorption will be described by diagrams of the type where -describes one photon absorption, - describes the successive absorption of - two photons, and - describes the simultaneous absorption of two photons [1-5].

Then three-photon optical transitions from the subband of heavy holes in the valence band to the conduction band generally have two types, which can be represented as a sum of different optical transitions depending on the initial state of electrons participating in optical transitions: if the initial state of electrons is in subband of heavy holes, then there are 16 different optical transitions, if the initial state of electrons is in the subband of light holes, then there are 22. Therefore, below we calculate the spectral dependence of the coefficient of three-photon absorption of light, let us consider for some of them.

The coefficient of interband three-photon light absorption is calculated as

$$K_{summ}^{(N)}(\omega, T) = \sum_{c, m'_c; v, m'_v} K_{c, m'_c; v, m'_v}^{(N)}(\omega, T) = \frac{N\hbar E}{I} \sum_{c, m'_c; \zeta, m'_\zeta; v, m'_v} W_{c, m'_c; \zeta, m'_\zeta; v, m'_v}^{(N)} \quad (1)$$

Here $K_{c, m'_c}^{(N)}(v, m'_v)(\omega, T)$ is partial interband three-photon absorption coefficient of light at which when calculating it is necessary sum over the intermediate states (at a fixed $(|\zeta, m'_\zeta\rangle)$ and final states $|c, m'_c\rangle(m'_c \pm 1/2)$); $K_{summ}^{(N)}(\omega, T)$ is total three-photon absorption coefficient of light, $W_{c, m'_c}^{(N)}(\zeta, m'_\zeta; v, m'_v)$ is the probability of the optical transition between the valence band and the conduction band, defined as

$$W_{c, m'_c; \zeta, m'_\zeta; v, m'_v}^{(N)} = \frac{2\pi}{\hbar} \sum_{\zeta, m'_\zeta} \left| M_{c, m'_c; \zeta, m'_\zeta; v, m'_v}^{(N)}(\mathbf{k}) \right|^2 \cdot [f_c(\mathbf{k}) - f_{v_l}(\mathbf{k})] \cdot \delta(E_c(\mathbf{k}) - E_{v_l}(\mathbf{k}) - N\hbar\omega) \quad (2)$$

where $|\zeta, m'_\zeta\rangle$ is the virtual state can be located both in the conduction band and in the subband of heavy holes $|V_{hh}, m'_{hh}\rangle(m'_{hh} = \pm 3/2)$ or in the subband of light holes $|V_{lh}, m'_{lh}\rangle(m'_{lh} = \pm 1/2)$, as well as in the spin-split subband $|SO, m'_{SO}\rangle(m'_{SO} = \pm 1/2)$ of the valence band, $M_{c, m'_c}^{(N)}(\xi, m'_\xi; v, m'_v)(\mathbf{k})$ is the composite matrix element of the optical transition under consideration, $f_c(\mathbf{k})[f_{v_l}(\mathbf{k})]$ are the distribution functions of current carriers, $E_c(\mathbf{k})[E_{v_l}(\mathbf{k})]$ is the energy spectrum of electrons (holes), is the eigenvalue of the total angular momentum

operator in the band with number $\nu(c, V_l, SO)$. The matrix element of the electron-photon interaction is defined as $H_{ll'} = \frac{e}{im_0\omega} \left(\frac{2\pi I}{n_\omega c}\right)^{1/2} (\vec{e} \cdot \vec{p})_{ll'}$, where \vec{p} is the operator is the momentum, \vec{A} is the vector potential of the electromagnetic wave, I is the intensity of light, and n_ω is the refractive index of the medium at the frequency ω .

Since the probability of a multiphoton optical transition, which is used to determine the coefficient of multiphoton light absorption, is expressed as

$$W_{c,m'_c;V,m'_V}^{(N)} = \frac{1}{\pi\hbar} \left(\frac{e}{m_0\omega}\right)^{2N} \left(\frac{2\pi I}{nc}\right)^N \left(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)}\right)^3 (N\hbar E - E_g)^{-1} \left| \mathfrak{R}_{c,m'_c;V,m'_V}^{(N)} \left(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)}\right)^2 \times \right. \\ \left. \left[f \left(E_c \left(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)} \right) \right) - f \left(E_{V_l} \left(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)} \right) \right) \right] \right| \quad (3)$$

where $k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)} = \left[\frac{2m_c m_{V_l}}{m_c + m_{V_l}} \right] (N\hbar\omega - E_g)$, $m_c(m_{V_l})$ is effective mass in the zone $c(V_l)$, $\left| \mathfrak{R}_{c,m'_c;V,m'_V}^{(N)} \left(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)}\right) \right|^2$ the quantity determined by the integral of the type $\int_{-1}^1 d\cos(\theta) \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi \int_0^\infty k dk^2 \sum_{\xi, m_s} \left| M_{c,m'_c;V,m'_V}^{(N)}(k, \theta, \varphi) \right|^2$, $f_c(k_{c,m_{hh}}^{(3\omega)}) \times [f_{hh}(k_{c,m_{hh}}^{(3\omega)})]$ is the distribution function of electrons (holes with energy $E_c(k_{c,m_{hh}}^{(3\omega)}) [E_{hh}(k_{c,m_{hh}}^{(3\omega)})]$). Let us

consider the specific case. Let $M_{c,m'_c;V,m'_V}^{(N)}(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)})$ is the composite matrix element consist of two terms, i.e.

$$M_{c,m'_c;V,m'_V}^{(N)}(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)}) = M_{c,m'_c;V,m'_V}^{(A)}(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)}) + M_{c,m'_c;V,m'_V}^{(B)}(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)}), \quad \text{where}$$

$M_{c,m'_c;V,m'_V}^{(A)}(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)})$ is the matrix element of the optical transition of the type “A”, and

$M_{c,m'_c;V,m'_V}^{(B)}(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)})$ is the matrix element of the optical transition of the type “B”

$$\left| M_{c,m'_c;V,m'_V}^{(N)}(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)}) \right|^2 = \\ = \left| M_{c,m'_c;V,m'_V}^{(A)}(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)}) + M_{c,m'_c;V,m'_V}^{(B)}(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)}) \right|^2 = \\ = \left| M_{c,m'_c;V,m'_V}^{(A)}(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)}) \right|^2 + \left| M_{c,m'_c;V,m'_V}^{(B)}(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)}) \right|^2 + \\ + \left[M_{c,m'_c;V,m'_V}^{(A)}(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)}) \right]^* M_{c,m'_c;V,m'_V}^{(B)}(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)}) + \\ + M_{c,m'_c;V,m'_V}^{(A)}(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)}) \left[M_{c,m'_c;V,m'_V}^{(B)}(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)}) \right]^*.$$

Whence we have that the total light absorption coefficient consists of the sum of the partial light absorption coefficients, determined by the quantities

$\left| M_{c,m'_c;V,m'_V}^{(A)}(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)}) \right|^2$ and $\left| M_{c,m'_c;V,m'_V}^{(B)}(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)}) \right|^2$, as well as the contributions to the total light absorption coefficient, determined by the quantity

$$\left[M_{c,m'_c;V,m'_V}^{(A)}(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)}) \right]^* M_{c,m'_c;V,m'_V}^{(B)}(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)}), \text{ i.e.} \\ K_{c,m'_c;V,m'_V}^{(A,B)}(\omega, T) = \frac{N \cdot E'}{I} W_{c,m'_c;V,m'_V}^{(A,B,C)} \quad (4)$$

where

$$W_{c,m'_c;V,m'_V}^{(A,B)} = \frac{1}{\pi\hbar} \left(\frac{e}{m_0\omega}\right)^{2N} \left(\frac{2\pi I}{nc}\right)^N \left(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)}\right)^3 (N\hbar E - E_g)^{-1} \left| M_{c,m'_c;V,m'_V}^{(A,B)}(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)}) \right|^2 \times$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left[f \left(E_c \left(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)} \right) \right) - f \left(E_{V_l} \left(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)} \right) \right) \right], \\
 W_{c,m'_c,V,m'_V}^{(C)} &= \frac{1}{\pi \hbar} \left(\frac{e}{m_0 \omega} \right)^{2N} \left(\frac{2\pi I}{nc} \right)^N \left(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)} \right)^3 (N\hbar E - E_g)^{-1} \left[f \left(E_c \left(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)} \right) \right) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - f \left(E_{V_l} \left(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)} \right) \right) \right] \times \\
 & \left[\left[M_{c,m'_c;\xi,m'_\xi;V,m'_V}^{(A)} \left(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)} \right) \right]^* M_{c,m'_c;\xi,m'_\xi;V,m'_V}^{(B)} \left(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)} \right) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + M_{c,m'_c;\zeta,m'_\zeta;V,m'_V}^{(A)} \left(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)} \right) \left[M_{c,m'_c;\xi,m'_\xi;V,m'_V}^{(B)} \left(k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)} \right) \right]^* \right]^2,
 \end{aligned}$$

calculating them separately, one can consider that the numerical contribution of the partial absorption coefficients of light. Therefore, we will consider specific optical transitions. For example, for an optical transition of the type $|V, -3/2\rangle \Rightarrow |V, +1/2\rangle \rightarrow |c, -1/2\rangle |V, -3/2\rangle \Rightarrow |V, -1/2\rangle \rightarrow |c, -1/2\rangle$, the coefficient of three-photon interband absorption of light for crystals of cubic symmetry is determined by the relation

$$\begin{aligned}
 K_{c,hh,1}^{(N=3)} &= \frac{3}{4} K_g^{(3)}(0) \frac{m_c m_{hh}}{(m_c + m_{hh}) m_0} I^2 \frac{E_g^2}{B^2 k_g^4} \left[f_c \left(k_{c,m_{hh}}^{(3\omega)} \right) - f_{hh} \left(k_{c,m_{hh}}^{(3\omega)} \right) \right] x_\omega^{-5} r_{c,m_{hh}}^{(3\omega)} \times \\
 & \quad \times \left[\left(\frac{2 \left(\frac{A}{B} - 1 \right)}{x_\omega} \right)^2 a_{c,hh,1}^{(N=3)} + 2 \frac{2 \left(\frac{A}{B} - 1 \right)}{-x_\omega} \frac{b_{c,hh,1}^{(N=3)}}{x_{lh} - x_{hh} - 2x_\omega} + \frac{c_{c,hh,1}^{(N=3)}}{(x_{lh} - x_{hh} - 2x_\omega)^2} \right] \quad (5)
 \end{aligned}$$

and for transitions of type $|V, -3/2\rangle \rightarrow |V, -3/2\rangle \rightarrow |V, -3/2\rangle \rightarrow |c, -1/2\rangle$, $|V, -3/2\rangle \rightarrow |V, -3/2\rangle \rightarrow |V, -3/2\rangle \rightarrow |c, -1/2\rangle$, $|V, -3/2\rangle \rightarrow |V, -1/2\rangle \rightarrow |V, -3/2\rangle \rightarrow |c, -1/2\rangle$, $|V, -3/2\rangle \rightarrow |V, -1/2\rangle \rightarrow |V, -1/2\rangle \rightarrow |c, -1/2\rangle$ we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 K_{c,hh,2}^{(N=3)} &= 6 K_g^{(3)}(0) \frac{m_c m_{hh}}{(m_c + m_{hh}) m_0} \times \\
 & \quad \times I^2 \left[f_c \left(k_{c,m_{hh}}^{(3\omega)} \right) - f_{hh} \left(k_{c,m_{hh}}^{(3\omega)} \right) \right] (x_\omega^{-5}) \left(r_{c,m_{hh}}^{(3\omega)} \right)^5 \times \\
 & \quad \times \left(a_{c,hh,2}^{(N=3)} \mathfrak{R}_1^2 + b_{c,hh,2}^{(N=3)} \mathfrak{R}_1 \mathfrak{R}_2 + c_{c,hh,2}^{(N=3)} \mathfrak{R}_2^2 \right) E_g^4
 \end{aligned}$$

where $K_g^{(3)}(0) = \pi m_0 \left(\frac{2\pi e^2}{n_\omega \hbar c} \right)^3 k_g^5 E_g^{-9} P_c^2 B^4$, $x_\omega = \hbar \omega / E_g$,

$k_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(3\omega)} = \frac{2m_c m_{V_l} 3\hbar \omega - E_g}{m_c + m_{V_l} \hbar^2}$, $x_l = E_l(k_\omega) / E_g$, $l = lh, hh, SO$, $r_{c,m_{V_l}}^{(N\omega)} = \frac{2m_c m_{V_l} N\hbar \omega - E_g}{m_c + m_{V_l} m_0 E_g}$, k_ω -is wave

vector of current carriers, determined by the energy conservation law $E_{lh}(k) - E_{hh}(k) - 3\hbar \omega = 0$, for linearly polarized light

$a_{c,hh,1}^{(N=3)} = \frac{90}{135}$, $b_{c,hh,1}^{(N=3)} = \frac{180}{135}$, $c_{c,hh,1}^{(N=3)} = \frac{488}{135}$, $a_{c,hh,2}^{(N=3)} = \frac{1}{15}$, $a_{c,hh,2}^{(N=3)} = \frac{1}{15}$, for circularly polarized light

$a_{c,hh,1}^{(N=3)} = \frac{70}{105}$, $b_{c,hh,1}^{(N=3)} = \frac{133}{105}$, $c_{c,hh,1}^{(N=3)} = \frac{396}{105}$, $a_{c,hh,2}^{(N=3)} = \frac{8}{105}$, $b_{c,hh,2}^{(N=3)} = \frac{13}{105}$, $c_{c,hh,2}^{(N=3)} = \frac{18}{105}$,

$$\mathfrak{R}_1 = \frac{2 \left(\frac{A}{B} - 1 \right)^2}{(\hbar \omega)^2} - \frac{2 \left(\frac{A}{B} - 1 \right)}{(E_{lh} - E_{hh} - 2\hbar \omega)(\hbar \omega)} + \frac{\frac{A}{B} + 1}{(E_{lh} - E_{hh} - 2\hbar \omega)(E_{lh} - E_{hh} - \hbar \omega)},$$

$$\mathfrak{R}_2 = - \frac{3}{2\hbar \omega (E_{lh} - E_{hh} - \hbar \omega)}$$

The spectral dependences of the coefficients of three-photon interband absorption of light for the above optical transitions are shown in Fig. 1. It can be seen from (Fig. 1) that the spectral

dependence of $K_{c, hh, 2}^{(N=3)} / K_g^{(3)}(0)$ depends on the type of optical transitions. In particular, for the first and second types of optical transitions, with an increase in the frequency of light, it increases and passing through a maximum decreases for both linearly polarized light and circularly polarized light, but the maxima of the dependence differ from each other in value. The numerical values of the band parameters of In Sb were taken from [6]

Figure 1. Spectral dependence of the coefficient of three-photon interband light absorption in InSb crystals for the two cases considered in the text

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ЭЛЕКТРООСАЖДЕНИЕ ОКОННОГО МАТЕРИАЛА ZnTe НА ПОДЛОЖКУ - СТЕКЛО/FTO

*Утамурадова Ш. Б., Далиев Х.С., Далиев Ш.Х., Музафарова С. А., Ачилов А.С.,
Музафарова Г.А., Хусанов З.М., Сапаров Ф.А., Кенжаева.З.С.*

*Научно-исследовательский институт физики полупроводников и микроэлектроники
при Национальном университете Узбекистана*

Авторами рассмотрены экспериментальные методы электроосаждения оконного материала ZnTe на подложку стекло/FTO и поглощающего материала CdTe на подложку стекло/FTO/CdS. Из-за отслаивания ZnTe в кислых ваннах CdS и CdTe вся конструкция устройств основана только на контакте стекло/FTO/CdS/CdTe/Au.

Перед нанесением ZnTe подложки тщательно промывали мыльной водой, метанолом, ацетоном, разбавленной HNO₃ и окончательно промывали ледяной уксусной кислотой. Подложки стекло/FTO промывали в деионизированной воде между различными растворителями, тогда как для очистки слоя стекло/FTO/CdS использовали только ледяную уксусную кислоту и промывали в деионизированной воде перед

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